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The Use of Stylometry in Recovering the work of Eighteenth-Century Women Writers: the Case of Elizabeth Sheridan Lefanu (1758-1837)

Elizabeth Sheridan Lefanu was until recently known primarily as the author of letters collected and published in the twentieth century under the title *Betsy Sheridan's Journal*. She published two novels under her married name, *The India Voyage* (1804) and *The Sister* (1810), which were not widely read at the time and have attracted little scholarly interest. Recent research activity has however resulted in three new attributions of authorship to Sheridan, transforming our views of her life and career. Aileen Douglas and Ian Campbell Ross have attributed to her two anonymously-published novels of the early 1780s, *Emeline; or, The Fairy Ring* (1780), and *The Triumph of Prudence over Passion* (1781); while both Douglas and Ross and Anna M. Fitzer agree that *Lucy Osmond*, published anonymously in 1803 but attributed variously to Alicia Sheridan Lefanu and to Alicia Lefanu, was also written by Elizabeth Sheridan. Not only do these attributions establish Elizabeth Sheridan as a significant woman writer in this period, they also create a significant line of female succession within the Sheridan-Lefanu family, dominated to date by generations of male writers.

Stylometry is a computational approach to authorship attribution that analyses linguistic patterns within texts to determine stylistic similarities and differences. Rooted in the premise that every writer has a distinct and often unconscious linguistic fingerprint, stylometry relies on statistical techniques to compare features such as word frequency, sentence structure, and lexical preferences across multiple texts. One of the most widely used methods in authorship attribution is Burrows' Delta, which calculates the statistical distance between texts based on most frequent words (MFW). By measuring the deviation of word frequency distributions, Burrows' Delta identifies stylistic affinities between texts, making it particularly effective for distinguishing between potential authors. In this study, we employed Burrows' Delta using the 100 most frequent words (MFW) as a key comparative metric, allowing for a robust and quantifiable assessment of authorship attribution in the case of Elizabeth Sheridan Lefanu.

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Rachel McCarthy is a PhD researcher at University College Cork, Ireland as part of CASCADE, a Horizon Europe MSCA and UKRO Doctoral Network. She is interested in using computational techniques such as stylometry, natural language processing, and language models to uncover new insights into literary and historical texts.